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CHANGES IN THE ACTIVITY OF SOME HYDROLYTIC ENZYMES DURING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN ATHLETES

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Abstract. Almost all biochemical processes in living matter, which are manifested by biochemical reactions, take place with the help of enzymes. Clearly, the vital activity of all living organisms is determined by the catalytic nature of the enzymes. The change in the oral pH of athlete judokas depending on nicotine consumption has been studied. It has been proven that the oral pH of athlete judokas changes depending on nicotine consumption. It has been established that the oral amylase Ph of non-smoking judokas has a weakly acidic, neutral reaction. It has been shown that increasing the acidity of the oral cavity of judokas weakens the specific activity of amylase and creates unfavorable conditions for the hydrolysis of starch in the oral cavity of judokas. With further increase in acidity, the catalytic activity of the enzyme amylase is minimized. It has been suggested that in order to increase the catalytic activity of oral amylase in judokas (to perfect hydrolysis of starch), it is best for judokas to use the so-called structured water during physical activity. Structured water promotes the formation of alkali in the oral cavity, allowing the enzyme amylase to maintain the pH optimum value and perform the corresponding catalytic action.

Keywords: Judoka, Athlete, Enzyme, Amylase, Hydrolysis, Nicotine.

Introduction. The unprecedented development of science in the XXI century has led to the emergence of new models of objects of study. There was a need to explain them using innovative technologies based on modern research. Often a person as a result of neglecting healthy habits himself becomes the cause of various diseases.

Enzymes are biological catalysts of a protein nature. Or even enzymes are specific high-efficiency, protein-catalyzed biological catalysts that are synthesized by living cells [1,4]. According to the modern classification, enzymes are divided into six main classes. Enzymes undergo the processes of hydrolysis, phosphorylation, synthesis, isomerization, oxidation-reduction and other processes in living organisms. Enzymes are actively involved in the food processing and digestion in living organisms. Almost all biochemical processes in living matter, which are manifested by biochemical reactions, are carried out with the help of enzymes [5]. Clearly the vital activity of all living organisms is determined by the catalytic nature of the enzymes.

A living cell contains up to 1000 different enzymes, each of which accelerates a particular biochemical reaction.

Enzymes themselves are synthesized in the human body. Of particular importance are hydrolytic enzymes, which in the human body in the digestive process mainly break down complex food molecules into simple substances. That is, they ensure good absorption of nutrients into the human body. Enzymes are a major component of human saliva. Saliva contains the following enzymes: lysozyme, amylase, phosphatases, etc. Enzymes have a specific property, which is expressed in the fact that each enzyme catalyzes either one chemical reaction or a group of one type of reaction.

Of particular importance from hydrolases are amylases. In the human body, amylase acts as an indicator during various biochemical reactions. Amylases, like other enzymes, are proteinaceous in nature. They affect the speed of biochemical reactions [3]. The biochemical activity of amylase is due to the fact that they can accelerate the hydrolysis of saliva-containing starch.

Aim and objectives of the research. Based on the above, the aim of the study was to change the amylase activity secreted from the body of athletes (oral cavity) depending on various factors. We aimed to solve the following tasks:

1. To determine the PH of saliva released from the mouth of athletes.
2. The effect of the reaction area on salivary amylase activity.
3. Alteration of salivary amylase activity depending on nicotine consumption.

Materials and methods. In order to achieve the set goal, 10 athletes - judokas participated in the experiment [6]. Age - (18-20) years. Judo training experience 6 years. Weight (60-70) kg. Judoists were selected from the wrestlers of the VIP judo team. The team is quite diverse. Judoists were selected from Guram Papitashvili Hall in Gori, where judo teams from different countries gather. Coaches: Anzor Tenadze, Ioseb Khukhashvili, Vepkho Bazandarashvili¹. One group was selected from these athletes. Group-1, non-smokers. We observed two more groups of 10 judokas in each. They were selected from amateur athlete judokas. The groups consisted mainly of judokas of the same age and weight category. Group-2, non-smokers and group-3 smokers.

In the experiment we used the following reagents: saliva of the mouth, diluted 10 times with distilled water, solution, diluted solutions of NaOH, HCL. Lugol's reagent (aqueous solution of KI and I₂), 1% starch solution - freshly made, Felling fluid (mixture of Felling solution # 1 and # 2), activator, inhibitor, etc.

Amylase activity was determined by the Volgemuth method [2]. According to Volgemuth, the method of determining amylase activity is based on finding the maximum dilution of saliva, during which complete dissolution of starch occurs. The unit of amylase activity is the amount of enzyme required to dissolve 1 ml of starch over 30 minutes at 37° C. Salivary amylase activity is expressed in the number of milliliters of 0.1% starch solution, which can dissolve 1 ml of undiluted saliva at 37°C for 30 minutes.

Discussion of research results. In the first phase of the study, we studied the amylase absorption spectrum in the ultraviolet area. As can be seen from the figure, Fig. 1 salivary amylase absorption is characterized by a maximum wavelength of 395 nm.

Fig 1. Amylase spectrum

It is essential to clarify the alkaline and acidic nature of amylase in athletes. Proper understanding of their ratio promotes the normal functioning of metabolic processes in athletes and enhances its resistance to various diseases. High acidity weakens the immune system in athletes. Less saliva is secreted into the oral cavity, demineralization of tooth enamel, caries and inflammation of the gums develop. The results of our study are given in Table №1.

Table №1. Changes in the pH of athletes's saliva depending on nicotine consumption.

	PH										
Group 1. (Non-smokers)	6.8	7.2	7.2	6.8	6.8	7.2	7.0	7.2	6.9	7.2	6.8-7.2
Group2. (Occasional smokers)	6.4	6.5	6.3	6.6	6.8	6.3	6.3	6.4	6.3	6.8	6.3-6.8
Group3. (Smokers)	5.0	5.6	4.9	5.6	5.3	4.9	5.1	5.6	4.9	5.6	4.9-5.6

As can be seen from Table 1, in nicotine-addicted (smoking) judokas, group 3, saliva PH values vary within (4.9-5.6). It is noteworthy that the enzyme amylase in its composition will have the same value of PH, therefore, Acidic area. The saliva PH of less-smoked athletes tends to be more neutral towards the neutral reaction area. Research has shown that the saliva of non-smoking judokas has a PH value (6.8-7.2). Ie In their case we have a weak acid-neutral area.

The next step we were interested in is the reaction to the effect of the salivary enzyme-amylase activity we studied. We observed according to the following scheme:

We took 5 test tubes in which we distributed the analytical substances as follows:

In the I test tube. 2 ml. Water + starch.

In the II test tube. 2 ml. Water + Amylase.

In the III test tube. 2 ml. Water + Starch + Amylase (smokers) + Gan. NaOH, two to three drops.

In the IV test tube. 2 ml. Water + Starch + Amylase (smokers) + Gan. HCl, two to three drops.

In the V the test tube. 2 ml. Water + Starch + Amylase (smokers) + Gan. HCl, two to three drops + NaOH, two to three drops.

We stirred the contents of the test tubes and added Lugol's solution to all test tubes. Hold the test tubes for 30 minutes and observe a change in the color intensity of the test tube contents. We used a water bath at 37-38° C. The sample tubes were incubated at the same temperature. The sample tubes were incubated at the same temperature. The first and second test tubes contained control samples. The observation showed that in the third test tube where the starch underwent alkaline hydrolysis by amylase in non-smoking athletes, the reaction went faster than in the fourth test tube. We believe that the amylase activity of the smokers in test tube IV was further attenuated by our reaction to an artificial increase in acidity. Increased acidity, led to a further weakening of the chemical activity of amylase in smoking athletes. Which is well illustrated by the change in color intensity of the contents of the test tubes over time and the biochemical reactions characteristic of hydrolysis: Lugol's solution and Felling reagent.

The following reaction takes place with the Felling reagent.

The hydrolysis reaction with Lugol's solution is as follows. In the IV tube.

By comparing the biochemical reactions in the contents of IV and V test tubes, we can conclude that the chemical activity of salivary amylase decreases depending on the consumption of nicotine and the higher its acidity.

Based on our research, biochemical methods can be developed that allow us to regulate the specific activity of oral amylase in athlete judokas during physical activity. One of such means is the so-called use of structured water in athlete judokas. The study of the kinetics of the action of the biochemical method will allow the athlete judokas to make even more perfect use of the methods of physical training that are a necessary condition for their sporting success (which is the task of our further research).

Conclusions

1. Athlete Judoists's oral PH varies depending on nicotine consumption.
2. Non-smoking judokas oral amylase PH has a weakly acidic, neutral reaction.
3. By increasing the acidity of the oral cavity of athlete judokas, the specific activity of the corresponding amylase is weakened.
4. Increasing the acidity of the oral cavity of athlete judokas creates unfavorable conditions for incomplete hydrolysis of relevant carbohydrates.
5. There is an opinion that sports judokas should use the so-called Structured water, which helps maintain the optimum PH of the oral cavity in them.

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